

Cardiomyocyte H9c2 cells present a valuable alternative to fish lethal testing for azoxystrobin

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Abstract: The present study aims at identifying, among six mammalian and fish cell lines, a sensitive cell line whose *in vitro* median inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) better matches the *in vivo* short-term *Sparus aurata* median lethal concentration (LC₅₀). IC₅₀s and LC₅₀ were assessed after exposure to the widely used fungicide azoxystrobin (AZX). Statistical results were relevant for most cell lines after 48 h of AZX exposure, being H9c2 the most sensitive cells, as well as the ones which provided the best prediction of fish toxicity, with a $LC_{50,96h}/IC_{50,48h} = 0.581$. H9c2 cell proliferation upon 72 h of AZX exposure revealed a $LC_{50,96h}/IC_{50,72h} = 0.998$. Therefore, identical absolute sensitivities were attained for both *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays. To conclude, the H9c2 cell-based assay is reliable and represents a suitable ethical alternative to conventional fish assays for AZX, and could be used to get valuable insights into the toxic effects of other pesticides.

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